

An easy access towards quinazolines via an improved protocol for ynones

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A simple and convenient method has been developed to accomplish Pt/2,2'-bipyridyl catalyzed acyl Sonogashira coupling for the efficient synthesis of ynones. The reaction display significant tolerance to various functional groups and the methodology has been successful in achieving fast reaction rate under relatively mild reaction conditions and low catalyst loading. Thus, the present method is found to be superior to palladium or copper catalyzed reactions in presence of phosphine ligand as reported earlier. Moreover, this methodology is unique as it offers a novel approach towards the construction of quinazoline pharmacophore and would surely grab the attention of the biological as well as pharmaceutical industries.

Keywords: Platinum catalysis, ligand, Sonogashira reaction, ynones, azaheterocycles.

Introduction

Quinazolines are an attractive class of heterocycles with diverse biological activities found in a variety of natural products as well as in pharmaceutically important compounds¹. For example, the natural product tryptanthrin represents a potential lead for new tuberculosis (TB) drugs. AZD3759 is an investigational drug with excellent central nervous system penetration capacity used against lung cancer. Fumiquinazoline S, a new quinazoline containing alkaloid marine-submerged wood, exhibited inhibition against Na⁺/K⁺-ATP_{ase}. Among other known drugs, Iressa is used for treatment of certain breast, lung and other cancers. Erlotinib is used in the treatment of several types of tumors, Prazosin acts as an R-adrenergic blocker etc. Owing to these broad ranges of biological activity, quinazolines have emerged as synthetic targets in the last few decades^{2,3}.

Variety of methods for the syntheses of quinazoline de-

rivatives have been developed so far⁴⁻⁶. For example, copper(I)-catalyzed Ullman-type reactions of amidine hydrochlorides with substituted 2-halobenzaldehydes furnished quinazoline derivatives. There are several reports on synthesis of quinazoline derivatives from nitriles/aldehydes and 2-aminobenzyl amines in presence of a copper catalyst or an oxidant such as IBX/PIDA etc. Although the previous methods for the synthesis of quinazoline derivatives are efficient, the employed starting materials often are not readily available and also difficult to prepare. Moreover, some of them required harsh reaction condition such as use of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and potassium permanganate as the oxidant, long reaction time etc. It is highly desirable to search for a more convenient and mild tandem reaction approach. Sequential transformations and multi-component one-pot reactions are always effective and environmentally acceptable and appear to be greener as compared to multi-step reactions. As part of our continuing interest to develop more efficient and envi-

Fig. 1. Structures of some quinazoline core containing bioactive heterocyclic scaffolds.

ronmentally benign methods in azaheterocycles⁷, we envisaged that synthesis of ynones under mild conditions can be used as a primary step for a tandem reaction sequence affording 2-substituted quinazoline derivatives.

Previous works:

This Work

Scheme 1. Previous and present synthetic approach towards quinazolines.

Catalytic coupling between acyl chloride and terminal alkyne utilizing palladium-copper catalysts, known as a Sonogashira-type reaction, remained as the major route for the construction of ynones for a long time⁸. The coupling of organic halides, poisonous carbon monoxide and terminal alkynes, known as carbonylative Sonogashira reaction, is not very encouraging in perspective of a green approach. But one of the demerits of copper co-catalyzed Sonogashira coupling is the formation of by-products from oxidative coupling of alkynes following the Hay/Glaser reaction⁹. To improve the efficiency of the reaction, silver, cadmium, copper, tin, thallium, gallium, stibium, indium, zinc etc. reagents along with carboxylic acid derivatives have been employed in order to achieve ynones^{10–13}. However, deployment of a large amount of transition metal/lanthanide catalyst made the reaction condition drastic and unsuitable for further

derivatization. In addition, the homogenous palladium catalysts often lose activity because of palladium metal aggregation and precipitation. Considering both environmental and economic issues, there is an urge to develop new environmentally benign catalytic system that should be efficient and can be easily recovered. Herein, we wish to report for the first time, a novel one-pot three-component synthesis of quinazolines via the platinum-catalyzed coupling of acid chlorides with terminal alkynes followed by *in situ* Michael addition and cyclocondensation of the resulting ynones with substituted 2-aminobenzylamines using air as the oxidant.

Experimental

Materials and method: All reagents were purchased from commercial suppliers and used without further purification, unless otherwise specified. Commercially supplied ethyl acetate and petroleum ether were distilled before use. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (100–200 mesh) and neutral alumina (100–200 mesh). Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on 0.25 mm extra-hard silica gel plates with a UV254 fluorescent indicator. The reported melting points are uncorrected. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at ambient temperature using 300 MHz spectrometers (300 MHz for ¹H and 75 MHz for ¹³C). Chemical shifts were reported in parts per million from the tetramethylsilane internal reference, and coupling constants were reported in Hertz. Proton multiplicities were represented as s (singlet), d (doublet), dd (double doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), and m (multiplet). Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr in reflection mode on a FTIR spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were done using an automated CHNS analyzer. Mass spectra (ESI-MS) were recorded on Waters Xevo G-2-SQ TOF electrospray ionization mass spectrophotometer.

General procedure for the synthesis of ynones (**3a–3m**):

To a 25 mL oven dried Rb flask was added PtBr₂ (8 mg, 0.002 mmol, 2 mol%), benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal (30 mg, 20 mol%) and 3 mL dry DMSO at ambient temperature under argon atmosphere. The mixture was stirred for 15 min. To this mixture were added sequentially potassium carbonate (276 mg, 2 mmol), phenyl acetylene (102 mg, 1 mmol), 2,2'-bipyridyl (30 mg, 20 mol%) and benzoyl chloride (140 mg, 1 mmol). The whole mixture was stirred at RT for 5 min

and then at 80°C for 45 min–1 h till the consumption of starting materials (monitored by TLC). After completion of reaction, the mixture was cooled to RT and diluted with ethyl acetate (40 mL) and washed with chilled water (10 mL×2) followed by brine (10 mL×1). The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The solvent was evaporated and the residue then purified by silica gel chromatography (100–200 mesh) with ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (2–6%, v/v) as the eluent to afford the products.

General procedure for the synthesis of quinazolines (4a–4i):

To a 25 mL oven dried Rb flask was added PtBr₂ (10 mg, 0.003 mmol, 3 mol%), benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal (30 mg, 20 mol%) and 3 mL dry DMSO at ambient temperature under argon atmosphere. The mixture was stirred for 15 min. To this mixture were added sequentially cesium carbonate (650 mg, 2 mmol), phenyl acetylene (102 mg, 1 mmol), 2,2'-bipyridyl (30 mg, 0.02 mol, 20 mol%), and benzoyl chloride (140 mg, 1 mmol). The whole mixture was stirred at RT for 5 min and then at 80°C for 1–1.5 h till the consumption of starting materials (monitored by TLC). Then the reaction mixture was cooled to RT and 2-aminobenzylamine (122 mg, 1 mmol) was added. The mixture was heated at 100°C for approx. 1 h (till the Michael addition was complete, monitored by TLC) under Ar atmosphere, and then heated in open air for another 1.5–2 h. After completion of reaction, the mixture was cooled to RT and diluted with ethyl acetate (30 mL) and washed with chilled water (10 mL×2) followed by brine (10 mL×1). The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The solvent then evaporated and the residue was purified by column chromatography (neutral alumina, 100–200 mesh) with ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (7–12%, v/v) as the eluent to afford the products quinazolines 4.

Characterization data of compound (3a–3m):

1,3-Diphenylprop-2-yn-1-one (3a): Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₀O; orange oil (0.194 g, 94%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.32–7.62 (8H, m), 8.46 (2H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 86.9, 93.1, 120.1, 128.6, 128.7, 129.6, 130.8, 133.1, 134.1, 136.9, 178.0; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₅H₁₀O+H]⁺: 207.0838, Found: 207.0839; IR (film, CH₂Cl₂): 2903, 2201, 1643, 1592, 1178, 743.

3-Phenyl-1-(*p*-tolyl)prop-2-yn-1-one (3b): Molecular for-

mula: C₁₆H₁₂O; brown solid (0.209 g, 95%); m.p. 67–69°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 2.36 (3H, s), 7.21–7.39 (5H, m), 7.60–7.61 (2H, m), 8.03 (2H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 21.8, 87.0, 92.6, 120.3, 128.4, 128.6, 128.7, 129.2, 129.3, 129.4, 129.7, 130.6, 132.5, 133.0, 134.6, 145.2, 177.7; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₆H₁₂O+H]⁺: 221.0961, Found: 221.0960; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2919, 2199, 1634, 1600, 1167, 745.

1-Phenyl-3-(*p*-tolyl)prop-2-yn-1-one (3c): Molecular formula: C₁₆H₁₂O; brown solid (0.198 g, 90%); m.p. 55–57°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 2.23 (3H, s), 7.06 (2H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz), 7.34–7.45 (5H, m), 8.07–8.10 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 21.7, 86.8, 93.9, 117.0, 128.6, 129.4, 129.5, 129.6, 133.1, 134.0, 137.0, 141.6, 178.0; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₆H₁₂O+H]⁺: 221.0961, Found: 221.0961; IR (film, CH₂Cl₂) cm⁻¹: 3031, 2194, 1637, 1601, 1292, 1009.

3-(*m*-Tolyl)-1-(*p*-tolyl)prop-2-yn-1-one (3d): Molecular formula: C₁₇H₁₄O; yellow solid (0.201 g, 86%); m.p. 98–100°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 2.30 (3H, s), 2.36 (3H, s), 7.22–7.25 (4H, m), 7.42 (2H, s), 8.05 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 21.2, 21.8, 86.8, 93.0, 120.0, 128.6, 129.3, 129.6, 129.7, 130.2, 131.7, 133.5, 134.7, 138.5, 145.2, 177.7; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₇H₁₄O+H]⁺: 235.1117, Found: 235.1118; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2918, 2192, 1630, 1602, 1309, 1166, 737.

3-(3-Phenylpropioyl)-2H-chromen-2-one (3e): Molecular formula: C₁₈H₁₀O₃; light yellow solid (0.214 g, 78%); m.p. 156–158°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 7.28–7.39 (5H, m), 7.48 (2H, t, *J* 3.6 Hz), 7.53–7.59 (1H, m), 7.66 (1H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz), 8.34 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 84.5, 94.8, 111.8, 116.7, 119.1, 121.9, 125.4, 128.9, 129.3, 129.9, 131.9, 133.1, 146.6, 153.3, 158.9; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₈H₁₁O₃+H]⁺: 275.0703, Found: 275.0702; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3060, 2213, 1723, 1601, 1488, 1051, 752.

1-(*p*-Tolyl)-3-(trimethylsilyl)prop-2-yn-1-one (3f): Molecular formula: C₁₃H₁₆OSi; orange oil (0.186 g, 86%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 0.01 (9H, s), 2.12 (3H, s), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz), 7.71 (2H, d, *J* 3.9 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.2, 22.6, 100.5, 101.7, 130.2, 130.3, 130.4, 131.3, 134.9, 145.9, 177.9; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₃H₁₆OSi+H]⁺: 217.1043, Found: 217.1044; IR (KBr)

cm^{-1} : IR (film, CH_2Cl_2) cm^{-1} : 2908, 2147, 1645, 1593, 840, 621.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenylprop-2-yn-1-one (3g): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{ClO}$; yellow solid (0.216 g, 90%); m.p. 101–103°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 7.28–7.41 (5H, m), 7.55–7.58 (2H, m), 8.04 (2H, d, J 4.2 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 86.4, 93.4, 119.6, 128.5, 128.7, 130.6, 130.8, 132.9, 135.1, 140.3, 176.3; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{ClO}+\text{H}]^+$: 241.0415, Found: 241.0415; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2912, 2201, 1652, 1602, 1487, 1076, 737.

1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-phenylprop-2-yn-1-one (3h): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$; yellow solid (0.210 g, 89%); m.p. 98–99°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 3.87 (3H, s), 6.97 (2H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.38–7.46 (3H, m), 7.64–7.67 (2H, m), 8.18 (2H, d, J 4.5 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 55.2, 86.4, 91.9, 119.9, 128.3, 129.9, 130.2, 131.5, 132.5, 164.1, 176.2; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2+\text{H}]^+$: 237.0900, Found: 237.0892; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3068, 2916, 2202, 1678, 1605, 1490, 1075.

1-(4-Nitrophenyl)-3-phenylprop-2-yn-1-one (3i): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3$; light yellow solid (0.171 g, 68%); m.p. 161–162°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 7.33–7.63 (5H, m), 8.27 (4H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 86.5, 95.4, 119.4, 123.8, 128.7, 130.4, 131.4, 133.1, 133.3, 141.0, 150.9, 175.8; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3+\text{H}]^+$: 252.0700, Found: 252.0691; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2911, 2201, 1649, 1608, 1445.

1-Cyclohexyl-3-phenylprop-2-yn-1-one (3j): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$; brown oil (0.165 g, 78%); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 1.61–2.07 (10H, m), 2.37–2.44 (1H, m), 7.19–7.36 (3H, m), 7.46–7.48 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 25.3, 25.8, 28.3, 52.2, 87.2, 91.2, 120.1, 128.5, 130.5, 132.9, 191.3; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}+\text{H}]^+$: 213.1300, Found: 213.1307; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2906, 2210, 1643, 1397, 1050, 845, 752.

1,3-Di-*p*-tolylprop-2-yn-1-one (3k): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$; yellow solid (0.208 g, 89%); m.p. 137–139°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 2.32 (3H, s), 2.36 (3H, s), 7.12–7.23 (4H, m), 7.49 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 8.03 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 21.3, 21.4, 30.5, 86.5, 92.9, 99.7, 108.3, 116.8, 128.9, 129.1, 129.3, 132.7, 133.6, 134.4, 141.0, 144.7, 177.4; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for

$[\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}+\text{H}]^+$: 235.1117, Found: 235.1118; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2903, 2204, 1648, 1054.

1-Phenylnon-2-yn-1-one (3l): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$; brown oil (0.149 g, 70%); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 0.90–0.93 (3H, m), 1.30–1.35 (4H, m), 1.43–1.52 (2H, m), 1.63–1.72 (2H, m), 2.47–2.52 (2H, m), 7.45–7.49 (2H, m), 7.55–7.65 (1H, m), 8.13–8.16 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 14.0, 19.2, 22.5, 27.8, 28.6, 31.2, 79.7, 96.9, 128.4, 128.5, 128.6, 129.5, 133.8, 137.0, 178.2; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}+\text{H}]^+$: 215.1430, Found: 215.1431; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2952, 2203, 1608, 1065, 938.

3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-yn-1-one (3m): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$; yellow solid (0.208 g, 89%); m.p. 146–148°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 3.85 (3H, s), 6.93 (2H, d, J 4.5 Hz), 7.51 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 7.60–7.66 (3H, m), 8.20–8.23 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 55.3, 86.9, 94.4, 111.9, 114.2, 114.5, 128.6, 129.5, 133.9, 134.0, 135.2, 137.1, 161.8, 178.1; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2+\text{H}]^+$: 237.0900, Found: 237.0912; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3219, 2914, 2213, 1644, 1588, 1091.

Characterization data of compound (4a–4i):

2-Phenylquinazoline (4a): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2$; yellow solid (0.144 g, 70%); m.p. 95–96°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 7.20–7.58 (4H, m), 7.82–7.88 (2H, m), 8.03 (1H, d, J 4.2 Hz), 8.52–8.56 (2H, m), 9.41 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): 123.6, 127.1, 127.3, 128.3, 128.6, 130.6, 133.1, 134.1, 138.0, 150.7, 160.5, 161.0; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2+\text{H}]^+$: 207.0922, Found: 207.0920; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2922, 1614, 1585, 1551, 1438, 1399, 730.

2-(*p*-Tolyl)quinazoline (4b): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2$; yellow solid (0.171 g, 78%); m.p. 121–122°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 2.34 (3H, s), 7.23–7.25 (2H, m), 7.43–7.48 (1H, m), 7.73–7.79 (2H, m), 7.96 (1H, d, J 9 Hz), 8.41 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 9.32 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 21.5, 123.5, 127.1, 128.4, 128.6, 129.2, 129.3, 129.4, 129.5, 134.0, 135.3, 140.9, 150.8, 160.4, 161.1; HRMS (ESI-TOF) m/z Calcd. for $[\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2+\text{H}]^+$: 220.1000, Found: 220.1001; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 2920, 1589, 1551, 1378, 725.

2-(*m*-Tolyl)quinazoline (4c): Molecular formula: $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2$; yellow solid (0.165 g, 75%); m.p. 92–94°C; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , Me_4Si): δ 2.42 (3H, s), 7.25 (1H, d, J 3.6 Hz), 7.35 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 7.53 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 7.83 (2H, t, J 9.0

Hz), 8.02 (1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 8.34 (2H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 9.38 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 21.5, 123.5, 125.8, 127.4, 128.5, 128.8, 129.1, 130.1, 131.4, 134.0, 137.4, 138.2, 150.8, 160.4, 161.2; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₅H₁₂N₂+H]⁺: 221.1073, Found: 221.1074; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2918, 1566, 1552, 1402, 740.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)quinazoline (4d): Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₂N₂O; off white solid (0.193 g, 82%); m.p. 90–92°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 7.01–7.09 (3H, m), 7.56–7.59 (1H, m), 7.82–7.90 (2H, m), 8.04 (1H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 8.57 (2H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz), 9.41 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 55.4, 113.9, 114.3, 123.3, 126.7, 127.1, 128.4, 130.2, 130.7, 131.9, 133.9, 137.4, 150.8, 160.3, 160.8, 161.8; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₅H₁₂N₂O+H]⁺: 237.1028, Found: 237.1020; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2928, 2853, 1585, 1410, 1242, 796, 733.

2-(4-Bromophenyl)quinazoline (4e): Molecular formula: C₁₄H₉BrN₂; yellow solid (0.214 g, 75%); m.p. 138–140°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 7.59–7.67 (3H, m), 7.87–7.92 (2H, m), 8.06 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 8.47–8.51 (2H, m), 9.42 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 123.6, 125.3, 127.1, 127.4, 128.6, 130.0, 130.2, 131.6, 134.2, 136.9, 150.6, 160.0, 160.4; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₄H₉BrN₂+H]⁺: 285.0027, Found: 285.0021; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2926, 1586, 1551, 1437, 1398, 730.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)quinazoline (4f): Molecular formula: C₁₄H₉ClN₂; yellow solid (0.170 g, 71%); m.p. 134–135°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 7.41 (2H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 7.53 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.79–7.84 (2H, m), 7.98 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 8.48 (2H, d, *J* 4.2 Hz), 9.35 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 123.6, 127.1, 127.4, 128.6, 128.8, 129.9, 134.2, 136.5, 136.8, 150.7, 160.0, 160.5; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₄H₉ClN₂+H]⁺: 241.0553, Found: 241.0551; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2923, 2851, 1587, 1505, 1438, 1380, 854, 778.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)quinazoline (4g): Molecular formula: C₁₄H₉FN₂; yellow solid (0.170 g, 71%); m.p. 134–135°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 7.09–7.19 (2H, m), 7.48–7.54 (1H, m), 7.78–7.83 (2H, m), 7.97 (1H, d, *J* 4.5 Hz), 8.53–8.58 (2H, m), 9.34 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 115.5 (*J*_{C-F} 11.2 Hz), 123.5, 127.2 (*J*_{C-F} 5.3 Hz), 128.6, 130.7 (*J*_{C-F} 4.5 Hz), 134.2 (*J*_{C-F} 4.5 Hz), 150.7, 160.3 (*J*_{C-F} 13.5 Hz), 163.0, 166.3; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for

[C₁₄H₉FN₂+H]⁺: 225.0828, Found: 225.0820; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3059, 2927, 1600, 1583, 1508, 1402, 1380, 855.

7-Chloro-2-phenylquinazoline (4h): Molecular formula: C₁₄H₉ClN₂; white solid (0.166 g, 69%); m.p. 128–130°C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 7.51–7.57 (3H, m), 7.86–7.88 (2H, m), 8.10 (1H, d, *J* 0.9 Hz), 8.61–8.62 (2H, m), 9.44 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 122.2, 128.0, 128.5, 128.6, 128.8, 128.9, 131.2, 137.9, 140.6, 151.6, 160.4, 162.1; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z*: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for [C₁₄H₉ClN₂+H]⁺: 241.0527, Found: 241.0528; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 2970, 1613, 1543, 1377, 872.

2-Hexylquinazoline (4i): Molecular formula: C₁₄H₁₈N₂; yellow oil; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, Me₄Si): δ 0.79–0.82 (3H, m), 1.26–1.36 (5H, m), 1.84–1.86 (2H, m), 2.52–2.56 (1H, m), 3.01–3.06 (2H, m), 7.21–7.52 (1H, m), 7.79–7.91 (3H, m), 9.26 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 14.0, 22.5, 28.9, 29.2, 31.6, 40.0, 123.0, 126.9, 128.2, 133.0, 133.9, 150.3, 160.3, 167.9; HRMS (ESI-TOF) *m/z* Calcd. for [C₁₄H₁₈N₂+H]⁺: 207.1011, Found: 207.1018; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3048, 2921, 1622, 1545, 1162, 836, 706.

Results and discussion

To study the possibility of our hypothesis for the N-benylation of various 3-aminocoumarin derivatives, our investigational journey was encouraged by the bipyridine catalyzed dimerization of aromatic terminal alkynes by Dash *et al.*^{14a} and copper free Sonogashira reaction by Fernandes *et al.*^{14b}. We have attempted initial experiments to materialize acyl Sonogashira reaction using the model substrate benzoyl chloride and phenyl acetylene and employing different metal catalysts as summarized in Table 1.

Commercially available, non-toxic benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal (10 mol%) was used as the additive for the platinum catalyst. Use of benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal for improving catalytic activity and proving better solubility of platinum catalysts has been described earlier¹⁵. In order to ascertain the role of common solvents in acyl Sonogashira reaction, we have checked toluene, 1,4-dioxan, acetonitrile, DMF, DMSO and NMP at temperatures 60–130°C while H₂O was not considered in this survey as we have planned a tandem reaction sequence. DMSO was found to be excellent solvent for the designed protocol. Polar solvents like acetonitrile under re-

Table 1. Optimization of acyl Sonogashira coupling reaction

Entry	Catalyst	Ligand	Base (2 eqv)	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Yield (%) ^a
1	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	KOH	DMSO	60	18
2	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	KO ^t Bu	DMSO	60	10
3	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	NaO ^t Bu	DMSO	60	–
4	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	Cs ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	60	40
5	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	Cs ₂ CO ₃ /K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	100	94
6	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	130	55
7	PtBr ₂	1,10-Phenanthroline	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	100	48
8	PtBr ₂	–	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	100	32 ^b
9	Pd(PPh ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	100	30
10	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	DMF	100	50
11	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	Dioxane	100	40
12	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	Toluene	100	Trace
13	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	100	47 ^c
14	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	CH ₃ CN	100	60 ^d
15	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	NMP	100	25
16	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	TEA	DMSO	80	76
17	PtBr ₂	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	RT	–
18	CuBr	2,2'-Bipyridyl	K ₂ CO ₃	DMSO	100	–

^aIsolated yields of pure products after 1.5 h; 10 mol% benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal was used as additive, ^breaction time: 6 h, ^c10 mol% ligand used, ^d10 mol% catalyst loading.

flux condition required higher catalyst loading (10 mol% Pt) to achieve the desired result. Small amount of catalyst loading (2 mol% PtBr₂) was effective to bring out the required transformation. Formation of ynone recorded at 60°C was 40%. However, 94% yield of the product ynone within a moderate period (1.5 h) was realized when the temperature was raised up to 100°C. Diverse ligands were subsequently screened to improve the yield and the optimum result was obtained with 20 mol% 2,2'-bipyridyl (Table S1).

Yield of the desired product **4a** was reduced on varying the ligand concentration to 10 mol% (Entry 13; Table 1).

A series of DMSO-tailored heterogeneous base systems were applied to bring out the cycloisomerization and it was observed that both Cs₂CO₃ and K₂CO₃ have provided same output. Considering cost factor and ease of handling, we have chosen K₂CO₃ as the base. Alkaline bases (e.g. KOH) re-

duced the yield of product whereas stronger bases like NaO^tBu/KO^tBu proved to be completely inefficient. In absence of 2,2'-bipyridyl ligand the reaction rate was very sluggish (Entry 8; Table 1) and only 32% ynone was isolated.

Though our main goal was to achieve the one-pot tandem reaction for the synthesis of quinazolines, but to judge the activity of the catalyst, we have isolated few ynones. As shown in Table 2, terminal alkynes with both *ortho*- and *meta*-substituent in the aryl groups gave excellent yields. Coumarin-3-carboxylic acid chloride derived ynone was also synthesized in good yield (Entry 4e; Table 2). Aliphatic alkynes such as 1-octyne, TMS-acetylene were also participated well in the acyl Sonogashira reaction to yield the corresponding ynones (Entry 3l, 3m; Table 2). Other aroyl chlorides such as 4-chlorobenzoyl, 1,4-anisoyl and 4-nitrobenzoyl chlorides were coupled with phenyl acetylene, affording the corresponding

Table 2. Synthesized ynones with their isolated yields in acyl Sonogashirareaction^a

^aReaction conditions: **1** (1 mmol), **2** (1 mmol), PtBr₂(2 mol%), 2,2'-bipyridyl (20 mol%), benzaldehy dedimethyl acetal (10 mol%), DMSO (3 mL), K₂CO₃ (2 mmol), 80°C, argon atmosphere, reaction time 45 min–1 h.

products **3g-3i** also with good yield (Table 2).

With optimized conditions in hand, we applied this methodology for the synthesis of a variety of quinazoline derivatives. The results are summarized in Table 3. As shown, all the substrates provided moderate to good yields at 100°C utilizing oxygen (air) as the oxidant. For a comparative study, the various terminal alkynes including electron donating and electron withdrawing aryl substituents (such as methyl, methoxy and halogen derivatives) and alkyl substituents were used. The yields were slightly reduced in presence of alkyl substituent (Entry 4i, Table 3). However, with TMS-acetylene, an unidentified compound was found instead of the quinazoline product, which must have resulted from base

catalyzed deprotection of TMS group.

To understand the reaction mechanism, 1.1 equiv. of 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione was treated with 2-aminobenzylamine under the standard reaction condition. However, 2-phenylquinazoline was not isolated from the post reaction mixture.

This result indicated that β-diketones were not likely to be the intermediates in this reaction. Formation of phenylglyoxal was observed along with quinazoline **4a**, when benzoyl chloride, phenyl acetylene and 2-amino benzylamine were employed in the one pot three component coupling reaction. Based on these aforementioned observations, a plausible reaction mechanism was proposed and shown in Scheme

Table 3. Substrate scope for the synthesis of 2-substituted quinazolines^{a,b}

^aReaction conditions: **1** (1 mmol), **2** (1 mmol), PtBr₂ (2 mol%), 2,2'-bipyridyl (20 mol%), benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal (10 mol%), DMSO (3 mL), K₂CO₃ (2 mmol), 80°C, argon atmosphere, reaction time: 45 min–1 h.

^bReaction conditions: 2-amino benzylamine (1 mmol), argon atmosphere 1 h, then 100°C, open air, 1.5-3 h.

Scheme 2. Controlled experiment performed to investigate the reaction mechanism.

3. The first step is the Michael addition of 2-aminobenzylamine to **3** to generate the enaminone intermediate A. Then the nucleophilic addition produced the intermediate B which upon hydrolysis of carbon-platinum bond followed by oxidative C-C bond cleavage leads to the generation of product **4**.

The structures of all the synthesized compounds were well characterized by spectroscopic analysis (¹H NMR, ¹³C

NMR, HRMS).

We have also performed the recovery and reuse of Pt-catalyst for the acyl Sonogashira reaction. Applying optimized conditions as shown in Table 1, we found that Pt catalyst can be reused after centrifugation followed by filtration of the post reaction mixture and subsequent treatment with water, little acetone and finally oven drying at 80°C. The activity of the recycled catalyst decreased after 1st run (approx. 6%) though allowing prolonged reaction time resulted in desired conversion in every repeated run (checked upto 4th run). Addition of bipyridyl ligand, K₂CO₃ and benzaldehyde dimethyl acetal (additive) was necessary in every repeated run. However, when used in tandem reaction sequence or in pres-

Scheme 3. Plausible mechanism for the formation of 2-substituted quinazolines.

Fig. 2. Recycling of Pt-catalyst over four runs.

ence of amines, the activity of the catalyst has decreased significantly and cannot be employed in next run.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have successfully developed a Pd/Cu free protocol for the acyl Sonogashira coupling reaction utilizing aromatic/aliphatic acyl chlorides and terminal alkynes in the presence of 2 mol% PtBr₂ and 20 mol% of bipyridyl ligand. The ligand screening shows that both the nature and the quantity of the ligand imposed significant influences on this transformation. We have established that the proper choice of catalyst, solvent and base are crucial for the completion of the reactions. A wide range of acyl chlorides, bearing not only aryl groups but also alkyl group and heterocyclic ring, effectively participates in the reactions. The usage of commercially available and inexpensive starting materials

and the efficacy in fabrication of multiple C-C and C-N bonds by a one pot domino reaction sequence makes these protocols potentially useful and attractive than the existing methods. Consequently, these methodologies extend the scope towards a wide range of novel compounds possessing an important structural subunit of a variety of biologically active molecules.

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